

OCEAN:ICE News – August 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to August's OCEAN:ICE News! We're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE.

Read on to meet our featured researcher of the month. Mark your calendars for the upcoming various events, such as Challenger Society Conference, European Polar Science Week, OCEAN:ICE, EPOC and PolarRES Annual Meetings, International Symposium on Polar Sciences at KOPRI, our exciting Climate Coffees and more!

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more news in September!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Yavor Kostov

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Yavor Kostov, an ocean/ice modeler at the [British Antarctic Survey](#).

Read the feature on Yavor [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE at Challenger Society Conference 2024

The Challenger Society for Marine Science is a UK learned society. Among other activities, they organise a biennial conference, which moves around the UK, and gathers a wide range of participants from all branches of marine science, often including a substantial contribution from the polar regions. This year the conference will be held on 2-6 September in Oban, Scotland. OCEAN:ICE [WP5](#) will be represented by [Mike Meredith](#) (the current president of the society), Rachael Sanders, and [Povl Abrahamsen](#), from [UKRI-BAS](#). [Chris Auckland](#) will also be presenting his recently published paper, closely aligned with work in OCEAN:ICE WP5. We look forward to presenting our results and plans to the rest of the UK marine science community and catching up with recent developments elsewhere.

For more information about the conference, and to register, go to <https://challenger2024.co.uk/>

OCEAN:ICE at Challenger Society Conference

2-6 September 2024 | Oban

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

OCEAN:ICE, PolarRES and PROTECT Joint Session at the 2024 European Polar Science Week

Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects, [OCEAN:ICE](#), [PolarRES](#) and [PROTECT](#), will jointly hold a session 'From Circulation Change to Sea Level Rise: the Polar Regions in the Earth System' at the [2024 European Polar Science Week](#) in Copenhagen. This joint session between three [EU Polar Cluster](#) projects will cover recent scientific advances made in both Polar Regions relating to climate and cryosphere. The three [EU Polar Cluster](#) projects cover related but different areas, and therefore blending the talks, will encourage new collaborations and networking across projects and between modelling as well as remote sensing communities.

For more information about OCEAN:ICE, PolarRES and PROTECT Joint Session at the European Polar Science Week go to our [website](#).

OCEAN:ICE, PolarRES and PROTECT
present...

Joint Session at European Polar Science Week

3 - 6 September 2024 | Copenhagen

OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation.

The PolarRES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme call H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2019-2020 under grant agreement Nr. 101003590.

The PROTECT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 869304.

Climate Coffee

Mathilde Helbert on [Temporal and spatial length scales in \$\delta^{18}\text{O}\$ observations](#)

5 September 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Mathilde Helbert

Temporal and spatial length scales in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observations

5 September 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Hjalte Jomo Danielsen Sørup on User Engagement in developing high-resolution Urban Heat Island models: CLIM4cities project

12 September 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Hjalte Jomo Danielsen Sørup

User Engagement in developing high-resolution Urban Heat Island models: CLIM4cities project

12 September 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

CLIM4CITIES

CLIM4cities is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

[Xabier Davila](#) on Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships
3 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Xabier Davila
Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships
3 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Ana Oliveira on CLIM4cities ML and AI Modelling
17 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Ana Oliveira
AI for Urban Climate: An EO-Based Approach for Heatwaves Exposure and Adaptation – CLIM4cities project
17 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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[Oliver Huhn](#) on [Record of Water Mass Age and Meltwater Fractions, Weddell Sea](#)

14 November 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Oliver Huhn

**Record of water mass age and meltwater
fractions, Weddell Sea**

14 November 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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OCEAN:ICE at EPOC & PolarRES Meetings 2024

OCEAN:ICE will take part in the upcoming [EPOC](#) (Reading 18-20th September 2024) and [PolarRES](#) (Potsdam 21-23 October 2024) annual meetings. [Andrew Meijers](#) will present on the progress and upcoming goals of OCEAN:ICE at both, and act as part of the expert advisory group advising EPOC on its progress. [Ruth Mottram](#) will also represent OCEAN:ICE where it complements her own work as a member of PolarRES.

In turn [Oliver Gutjahr](#) from EPOC will attend the OCEAN:ICE annual meeting (Copenhagen 23-25 September 2024) to discuss areas of overlap and complementary research, notably in modelling of the AMOC.

OCEAN:ICE at International Symposium on Polar Sciences at KOPRI

The 29th International Symposium on Polar Sciences (ISPS2024) is organised by [KOPRI](#) on September 30 to October 1st, 2024, in Incheon. The first ISPS was held in 1988, and the meeting was initially organised every other year. After 1999 it has been an annual event where about 100 leading international polar scientists meet and discuss science, collaboration, logistics and strategy at the KOPRI facilities in Incheon. During the COVID years the meeting was online, and the participation rose to 400 per meeting.

ISPS2024 commemorates the 10th anniversary of the Antarctic Jang Bogo Station in Terra Nova Bay with the theme entitled "Scientific Advances based on Antarctic Jang Bogo Station over the Last 10 Years", and aims to showcase the expanded research portfolio made possible by the station's establishment. Jang Bogo Station is a year-round facility offering optimal research opportunities for investigating various polar phenomena, including the cryosphere, geosphere, and hydrosphere. It has played a crucial role in understanding climate change and the Antarctic system's response to it.

[Abstract Submission](#): from July 26 to August 23

[Registration](#): from July 26 to August 30

The OCEAN:ICE project will be represented by the [WP2](#) co-lead [Anna Wählén](#).

For more enquiries, please contact the symposium secretariat at symposium@kopri.re.kr

Programme

[ISPS2024 agenda](#)

OCEAN:ICE at International Symposium on Polar Sciences at KOPRI

30 September - 1 October 2024 | Incheon

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Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 19-23 August 2024, [11th SCAR Open Science Conference](#), Pucón & online
- 21-23 August 2024, [Nordic Meteorologist Meeting](#), Copenhagen
- 2-6 September 2024, [Challenger Society Conference](#), Oban
- 3-6 September 2024, [European Polar Science Week](#), Copenhagen
- 18-20 September 2024, [EPOC](#) Annual Meeting, Reading
- 23-25 September 2024, OCEAN:ICE and IAPSO Joint Event, Copenhagen & online
- 30 September - 1 October 2024, 29th International Symposium on Polar Sciences, Incheon
- 21-23 October 2024, [PolarRES](#) Annual Meeting, Potsdam

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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